

DMIS Lab at MedHopQA-2025: Ensemble Multi-Retrieval Methodologies with Reasoning Language Model Decision

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Abstract

Robust and trustworthy biomedical question answering (QA) remains a critical challenge for large language models (LLMs), especially in complex domains such as rare diseases, where information is fragmented across multiple sources. MedHopQA 2025 benchmark introduces 10,000 multi-step reasoning questions curated from Wikipedia, requiring systems to extract, connect, and synthesize biomedical knowledge across interlinked documents. In this work, we present a retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) and decision-making framework that integrates diverse retrieval strategies, including Query2Doc-based, Rationale-based, and Web-augmented retrieval, and employs a dedicated decision-maker model to select or directly generate the most accurate and well-reasoned answers. Our system not only leverages evidence from both Wikipedia and the web but also explicitly evaluates and compares candidate answers to ensure answer reliability and reasoning transparency. Experiments on the test set demonstrate that our ensemble approach achieves state-of-the-art performance, highlighting the importance of hybrid retrieval and robust decision-making in advancing biomedical multi-step QA.

Keywords

Medical Question Answering, Retrieval Augmented Generation, Query Decomposition

1. Introduction

Large language models (LLMs) have rapidly advanced the frontier of natural language processing (NLP), demonstrating remarkable capabilities across a range of domains. In biomedical and healthcare applications, however, the stakes are uniquely high: robust and trustworthy question answering (QA) systems are required to ensure reliable decision-making and knowledge dissemination. While numerous biomedical QA benchmarks, such as PubMedQA [1], BioASQ [2], and MedQA [3], have driven progress in single-hop factoid retrieval and reasoning, the ability of LLMs to perform multi-step reasoning remains insufficiently explored, especially in complex domains like rare diseases, where information is dispersed and context-dependent.

To address these limitations, the MedHopQA 2025 [4] task introduces a challenging new benchmark: a collection of 10,000 expert-curated multi-step reasoning QA pairs derived from Wikipedia, focusing on diseases, genes, and chemicals, with an emphasis on rare conditions. Unlike prior datasets that typically target single-source fact extraction, MedHopQA questions require models to extract, connect, and synthesize information across multiple interlinked sources, mimicking the real-world process of clinical and biomedical inquiry.

In this work, we present a multi-step retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) and decision-making framework designed for MedHopQA. Our system combines multiple retrieval and reasoning strategies, integrating evidence from both Wikipedia and web. We leverage frameworks such as Query2Doc [5], Rationale-based retrieval, and Web search-augmented retrieval to generate candidate answers [6], and

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employ a dedicated decision-maker model [7] to select the most accurate and well-supported response, or to directly answer the question when candidates are insufficient. This ensemble approach ensures that both direct factual correctness and the underlying multi-hop reasoning are faithfully addressed.

Our method achieves state-of-the-art performance on the MedHopQA leaderboard, demonstrating the effectiveness of hybrid retrieval and robust LLM-based reasoning in tackling complex, multi-source biomedical question answering.

2. Related Works

Retrieval-augmented large language models (LLMs) have emerged as a powerful paradigm for biomedical question answering, where trustworthy evidence must be gathered from multiple documents before a conclusion can be drawn [8, 9, 10]. This paradigm is directly relevant to the MedHopQA task, which requires multi-hop reasoning over various biomedical sources.

Recent works have increasingly focused on leveraging LLM-generated intermediate text (e.g., pseudo-documents, rationales) to guide retrieval toward relevant information. Query2doc [5] proposes a query-expansion strategy in which an instruction-tuned LLM is prompted to “*write a passage that can answer the query.*” The resulting pseudo-document is concatenated with the original question and submitted to a retriever. Because the synthetic passage typically introduces domain synonyms, acronyms, and MeSH terms absent from the user query, the method successfully recalls appropriate documents when searching biomedical repositories.

Rationale-Guided Retrieval Augmented Generation (also referred to as RAG²) [11] explicitly incorporates chain-of-thought reasoning into the retrieval loop. The LLM first breaks down the medical question by producing a multi-step rationale. Each rationale segment is treated as a refined search query, retrieving passages from diverse biomedical sources including PubMed, clinical guidelines, and textbooks, and a lightweight filter discards snippets that do not increase the rationale’s likelihood. The selected evidence is then fed back to the LLM to generate the final answer, thereby tightly coupling evidence collection with reasoning.

These lines of work demonstrate complementary ways in which LLM-generated intermediate pseudo-documents, or explicit rationales, can guide retrieval toward information that supports multi-hop biomedical reasoning, a core requirement to MedHopQA.

3. Methods

We designed a multi-step RAG and decision-making framework to address the MedHopQA 2025 task, which involves generating both a short answer (the direct response) and a long answer (the supporting reasoning) for each question.

3.1. Retrieval-Augmented Generation Framework

Our RAG approach integrates multiple methodologies to robustly generate answers by leveraging various external knowledge sources from Wikipedia and the web. We detail our procedure as follows:

3.1.1. Query2Doc-Based Retrieval and Answer Generation

For a given question q , we first convert it to a search-oriented query q' using the Query2Doc approach. Query2Doc leverages an LLM to reformulate the original question into a more informative passage that can better assist in retrieving relevant information for answering the question:

$$q' = \text{Query2Doc}(q)$$

This query q' is then used to retrieve the top N number of documents D_{ret} from a Wikipedia-based corpus [12] using a retriever \mathcal{S} :

$$D_{\text{ret}} = \mathcal{S}(q', \text{Wikipedia})$$

Figure 1: Overview of our multi-step RAG ensemble. Three answer candidates are generated via (A) Query2Doc-based with Wikipedia retrieval, (B) Rationale-based with Wikipedia retrieval, and (C) Web Search API applied. The decision maker then compares the candidates and selects the final answer pair or generates additional reasoning for the decision.

The retrieved documents are then passed through a reranker \mathcal{R} to select the top N passages D_{rank} :

$$D_{\text{rank}} = \mathcal{R}(D_{\text{ret}})$$

The refined document set D_{rank} is provided as the context to model \mathcal{M} to generate the short answer s^1 and the long answer l^1 :

$$(s^1, l^1) = \mathcal{M}(q, D_{\text{rank}})$$

3.1.2. Rationale-Based Retrieval and Answer Generation

In parallel, we utilize a dedicated model $\mathcal{M}_{\text{rationale}}$ to generate a rationale-augmented query. This approach uses an LLM to generate an answer containing rationale for the original question, which is then used as a query to retrieve documents relevant to that rationale-augmented perspective:

$$q'' = \mathcal{M}_{\text{rationale}}(q)$$

This refined query q'' is then used to retrieve the top N number of documents from the Wikipedia corpus via the same retriever \mathcal{S} , followed by passage selection through the reranker \mathcal{R} :

$$D_{\text{rank}} = \mathcal{R}(\mathcal{S}(q'', \text{Wikipedia}))$$

The final context D_{rank} is given to the model \mathcal{M} to generate both s^2 and l^2 :

$$(s^2, l^2) = \mathcal{M}(q, D_{\text{rank}})$$

3.1.3. Web Search-Augmented Retrieval and Answer Generation

To complement the above Wikipedia-based retrieval strategies, we employ a separate model \mathcal{M}_{web} , which is specifically augmented with web search capabilities:

$$(s^3, l^3) = \mathcal{M}_{\text{web}}(q)$$

3.2. Decision-Making Stage

Throughout the decision-making process, we utilize a dedicated decision maker model \mathcal{M}_{dec} . This model systematically compares the three candidate answer pairs generated by different retrieval-augmented methods, then selects the candidate it determines to be the most accurate and relevant, or directly answers the question itself if none of the candidates are deemed suitable. In this way, \mathcal{M}_{dec} ensures the

generation of a reliable and accurate final response, even in cases where previous methods either fail to produce an answer or generate incorrect ones.

1. The three candidate answer pairs $\{(S^i, L^i)\}_{i=1}^3$ generated from the retrieval-augmented methods (in Sections 3.1) are compared. The decision maker model \mathcal{M}_{dec} is employed to assess their accuracy, relevance, and internal consistency, thereby guiding to the most suitable answer pair.
2. If none of the three answers are deemed correct, an additional reasoning step is invoked. In this case, \mathcal{M}_{dec} directly answers the question q in question set Q .

$$(S, L) = \begin{cases} (S^i, L^i) & \text{if a suitable candidate } i \in \{1, 2, 3\} \text{ exists} \\ \mathcal{M}_{\text{dec}}(Q) & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

This ensures that final answer selection is consistently grounded in both external retrieval evidence and robust LLM-based reasoning.

4. Experimental Settings

4.1. Dataset and Metric

To evaluate our framework, we utilize the benchmark dataset provided by the MedHopQA 2025 task. This dataset comprises questions that require multi-step reasoning to answer correctly.

For each question in the development set (a total of 45 questions), it includes ground truth short and long answers. We first evaluate performance by focusing solely on the short answers in the development set. Specifically, we check the Exact Match (EM) score employed by MedHopQA 2025 organizer, which measures the proportion of short answers that exactly match the ground truth after applying a series of normalization steps, such as lowercasing and the removal of articles. The final EM score is computed as the number of exactly matching short answers divided by the total number of questions.

For the test set, which is a total of 10,000 questions, no ground truth answer is given. Also, two additional evaluation metrics were exclusively applied to the test set: Improved EM Score and Concept-Level Score. The Improved EM Score applies an enhanced normalization algorithm to the standard EM metric, aiming to more accurately reflect answer correctness in the presence of minor textual variations. The Concept-Level Score leverages curated synonym dictionaries and biomedical ontologies to account for semantic equivalence, granting credit to predictions that are meaningfully identical to the gold answer even if their surface forms differ.

4.2. Model and Document selection

Our methodology allows for flexible configurations depending on the models employed and the number of contextual documents used for answer generation. Here, we adopt the following experimental setup:

For the RAG stage utilizing Query2Doc, we employ GPT-4o [13] for both query expansion and answer generation to generate concise and accurate expansions that effectively bridge gaps in the initial query and improve retrieval coverage. Document retrieval is performed using an ElasticSearch [14, 15] built over a Wikipedia corpus. This corpus was constructed by chunking the raw text using langchain [16]’s RecursiveCharacterTextSplitter, where each chunk contains a maximum of 100 words with a 10-word overlap between adjacent chunks. From this corpus, 1,000 documents are retrieved, and the top 200 documents are then selected as context using MedCPT [17] cross-encoder for reranking.

For the RAG stage using Rationale-augmented query, we adopt the o3 [7] model for question reformulation, leveraging its exceptional reasoning capabilities to create more focused and clinically relevant question variants. Answer generation is again performed by GPT-4o. We use the same ElasticSearch over the Wikipedia corpus to retrieve 1,000 documents, followed by reranking with MedCPT to select the top 200 as context.

For the RAG stage based on Web Search, we utilize Gemini 2.5 Pro [18] in combination with the Google Search tool [6]. This setup enables broader retrieval from the open web, complementing pre-downloaded and processed corpus-based methods and providing additional perspectives.

For the Decision-Making stage, we adopt the o3 model following its advanced reasoning and contextual understanding capabilities, which enable it to critically evaluate multiple candidate answers and identify the most accurate response. This makes it particularly well-suited for the decision-making stage, where synthesizing and selecting the best answer from diverse retrieval sources is essential.

With the exception of the o3 model, which does not have a temperature setting, all other models were configured with a temperature of 0 to ensure deterministic outputs.

5. Results

To demonstrate the performance of our framework, we present two sets of results: (i) an EM analysis on the development set, and (ii) an EM, Improved EM, Concept-Level analysis on the test set.

5.1. Analysis on the development dataset

Table 1

Score comparison between various methods. *Dense retrieval* was conducted using vector embeddings generated by the Cohere Embed v3 model [19], leveraging the publicly available Cohere/wikipedia-2023-11-embed-multilingual-v3 [20] dataset hosted on Hugging Face. *Sparse retrieval* was conducted using an ElasticSearch built on a Wikipedia corpus. All methods except GPT-4o (first row) employed MedCPT as the reranker.

Method	Score
GPT-4o	0.60
GPT-4o + Dense Retrieval (single turn)	0.76
GPT-4o + Dense Retrieval (multi-turn)	0.82
GPT-4o + Sparse Retrieval (multi-turn)	0.80
w/ Query2Doc	0.87

As summarized in Table 1, our approach exhibits a clear performance advantage across various retrieval strategies.

When GPT-4o was asked to generate answers without any context, it achieved only 0.60 in EM score.

Providing the top 16 retrieved documents from the Wikipedia corpus using a dense retriever resulted in an EM score of 0.76. For cases where the model failed to generate a definitive answer from this initial context, we performed a second trial by providing an expanded context of the top 32 documents for these specific unanswered questions, which increased the final EM score to 0.82.

When using a sparse retriever with GPT-4o, the EM score reached 0.80. While this was slightly lower than the dense retriever result, the sparse retriever offered significantly faster retrieval speed with comparable performance, making it a compelling choice.

Furthermore, when queries were generated using the Query2Doc technique prior to document retrieval, the EM score improved substantially. We experimented with various numbers of top-k documents for context, and after submitting the best-performing result from using the top 200 documents to the scoring site, we achieved an EM score of 0.87. This result underscores the significant benefit of pseudo-document generation in enhancing retrieval coverage and, consequently, answer accuracy.

5.2. Analysis on the test dataset

Table 2

Comparison of EM Score, Improved EM Score, and Concept-Level Score across all five test set runs. Run 4 represents our final submission recorded on the official leaderboard.

Run #	EM Score	Improved EM Score	Concept Level Score
1	0.78	0.79	0.83
2	0.86	0.88	0.90
3	0.84	0.85	0.89
4	0.84	0.85	0.89
5	0.84	0.85	0.89

We conducted a total of five submissions on the test set, exploring a range of answering strategies.

Run 1. As a preliminary experiment, the first run starts with retrieving 1,000 documents using a sparse retriever, followed by MedCPT reranking to select the top 16 documents, which were provided to GPT-4o along with the question for answer generation. Subsequently, a separate attempt was conducted using the top 128 documents from sparse retrieval, and an additional, independent attempt was made using the top 32 documents obtained through dense retrieval. Finally, the question was passed to GPT-4o and o3, respectively, without any context. Each subsequent stage was applied only to questions for which the previous step failed to produce an answer (i.e., marked as “unknown” or “not found in context”). This framework resulted in an EM score of 0.78 and a Concept-Level Score of 0.83.

Run 2. To verify whether the effectiveness of query transformation observed on the development set generalizes to the test set, we apply the *Query2Doc* method to reformulate the questions. Using the transformed queries, 1,000 documents were retrieved via a sparse retriever and reranked using MedCPT to select the top 16 documents. The reformulated question and corresponding context were then provided to GPT-4o. For questions still unanswered, responses were generated by the o3 model without any context. This approach achieved an EM score of 0.86 and a Concept-Level Score of 0.90, demonstrating the effectiveness of query transformation on the test set as well.

Runs 3 and 4. The insight from Run 1 highlighted the necessity of multiple iterations to handle challenging questions, while Run 2 showed the performance gain from applying question transformation. Based on them, we design our final framework, described in Section 3 and configured with the settings detailed in Section 4.2, which combines multi-retrieval signals with a reasoning-based decision process.

We check the score of Run 3 using our final framework, achieving an EM score of 0.84 and a Concept-Level Score of 0.89. Although these scores were slightly lower than those in Run 2, we consider this approach preferable due to its ability to systematically refine answers using the o3 decision-maker, rather than relying on manual iterative correction as was performed in Run 1. In this process, when the o3 decision-maker determined that all candidate answers were inadequate, it generated its own answer, which occurred in 5.1% of the cases. To confirm the robustness of our method, we repeated the same configuration in Run 4, which yielded identical scores. Run 4 is subsequently submitted as our official final entry on the leaderboard.

Run 5. As a final attempt to improve performance beyond Run 4, we extend our framework by adding an additional step after the o3 decision-making stage: we incorporated Claude 3.7 Sonnet [21] with Web Search, with the expectation that it might correct suboptimal decisions made by o3. However, this configuration did not yield any performance improvement over Run 4. Consequently, we did not adopt this variant as part of our final framework.

6. Conclusion

In this study, we address the MedHopQA 2025 challenge, which focuses on multi-step biomedical question answering requiring the integration and reasoning over information distributed across multiple sources. We propose a retrieval-augmented generation and decision-making framework that leverages diverse retrieval strategies, including *Query2Doc*-based, Rationale-based, and Web-augmented retrieval, coupled with a robust decision maker model to select or generate the most accurate and well-reasoned answers.

Our results demonstrate that combining multiple retrieval and reasoning frameworks can significantly enhance the ability of LLM-based systems to handle complex, multi-hop biomedical questions, particularly in domains such as rare diseases where knowledge is both specialized and interconnected. Our approach achieved the highest performance on the leaderboard, validating the effectiveness of ensemble retrieval and decision-based answer selection.

The success of our system underscores the importance of integrating external evidence, flexible retrieval strategies, and explicit reasoning mechanisms in advancing biomedical QA. Future work may further explore fine-grained reasoning analysis, improved explanation generation, and adaptation to other high-stakes domains requiring trustworthy multi-step inference.

Limitations

Closed-source model dependency. Our framework relies on several closed-source models, including GPT-4o, o3, and Gemini 2.5 Pro, which were selected for their outstanding performance in question answering and reasoning tasks. However, the use of closed-source models poses challenges to reproducibility, as their performance may change unexpectedly due to updates or other factors beyond our control.

Latency and cost considerations. Our framework depends on API calls to generate results, which introduces network latency. In particular, the Query2Doc and Rationale-augmentation stages involve additional API calls to reformulate the initial queries, further increasing latency. Additionally, using models with relatively high costs, such as o3 for the rationale-augmentation stage and the final decision-making stage, imposes significant financial burdens.

Declaration on Generative AI

During the preparation of this work, the author(s) used GPT 4o in order to: Grammar and spelling check.

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A. Appendix

A.1. Prompts

A.1.1. Prompts to generate answer

System prompt

```
You are a medical QA assistant.
The following is a question about medical knowledge.
You are given multiple retrieved documents as reference context.
1. Use only the information contained in those documents.
  - Do NOT hallucinate or invent facts.
2. Think step-by-step:
  • First, reason through the relevant information.
  • Then give a concise Short Answer (1-3 words).
3. Short Answer formatting rules
  • Preserve the entity's full official name.
  - Type 2 → "Diabetes mellitus, type 2"
  - Factor VIII → Factor VIII deficiency
  - 2 → "Chromosome 2"
  - Carpenter's → Carpenter's syndrome
  - NPH → Normal Pressure Hydrocephalus
  • For yes/no questions, reply exactly Yes or No.
4. You are strongly required to follow the specified output format;
   conclude your response with the phrase "Therefore the answer is [ANSWER].".
```

User prompt

```
{question or pseudo-document}
Retrieved context:
[1] Title: {title_1}
Text: {text_1}
[2] Title: {title_2}
Text: {text_2}

...

[N] Title: {title_N}
Text: {text_N}
```

A.1.2. Prompts of Query2Doc-based query reformulation

System prompt

```
You are a helpful assistant.
```

User prompt

Write a medical passage that can help answer the given query.
Include key information or terminology for the answer.

Example:

Query: A 39-year-old woman presents to the family medicine clinic to be evaluated by her physician for weight gain. ... Which of the following recommendations may be appropriate for the patient at this time? A) Hepatitis B vaccination B) Low-dose chest CT C) Hepatitis C vaccination D) Shingles vaccination

Passage: Against vaccine-preventable diseases. Every visit by an adult to a healthcare provider should be an opportunity to provide this protection. ...

Query: A 23-year-old male presents to his primary care physician after an injury during a rugby game. ... Which of the following is the most likely diagnosis? A) Medial collateral ligament tear B) Lateral collateral ligament tear C) Anterior cruciate ligament tear D) Posterior cruciate ligament tear

Passage: Diagnosing PCL Injuries: History, Physical Examination, Imaging Studies, Arthroscopic Evaluation. ...

Query: A 45-year-old woman is in a high-speed motor vehicle accident and suffers multiple injuries ... Which of the following is an appropriate next step? A) Provide transfusions as needed B) Withhold transfusion based on husband's request C) Obtain an ethics consult D) Obtain a court order for transfusion

Passage: Legal and ethical issues in safe blood transfusion. ...

Query: A 4-year-old male is accompanied by his mother to the pediatrician. ... Which of the following would most likely be found on biopsy of this patient's kidney? A) Mononuclear and eosinophilic infiltrate B) Replacement of renal parenchyma with foamy histiocytes C) Destruction of the proximal tubule and medullary thick ascending limb D) Tubular colloid casts with diffuse lymphoplasmacytic infiltrate

Passage: The natural history of urinary infection in adults. ...

Query: {question}

Passage:

A.1.3. Prompts of Rationale-based query reformulation

System prompt

You are a medical expert.

User prompt

{question}

A.1.4. Prompts of Web Search-augmented retrieval stage

System prompt

You are a medical QA assistant.

The following is a question about medical knowledge.

You will use **Google Search** to retrieve relevant information. This retrieved information will serve as your **sole reference context**.

1. Base your answer **exclusively** on the information retrieved through your Google Search.
 - * Do **NOT** use any prior knowledge.
 - * Do **NOT** hallucinate or invent facts.
2. Think step-by-step:
 - * First, identify the key information from your search results relevant to the question.
 - * Then, reason through this retrieved information to formulate your answer.
 - * Finally, provide a **concise Short Answer** (1-3 words).
3. Short Answer formatting rules:
 - * Preserve the entity's **full official name**.
 - * Type 2 → "Diabetes mellitus, type "2
 - * Factor VIII → "Factor VIII "deficiency
 - * 2 → "Chromosome "2
 - * Carpenter's → "Carpenter's "syndrome
 - * NPH → "Normal Pressure "Hydrocephalus
 - * For yes/no questions, reply **exactly** \"Yes\" or \"No\".
4. You are strongly required to follow the specified output format; conclude your response with the phrase "Therefore the answer is [ANSWER]."

User prompt

{question}

A.1.5. Prompts of decision-making stage

System prompt

You are an expert decision-making assistant.

Please carefully analyze these three answers and choose the **best** one. Follow these steps:

1. **Identify the key decision criteria** (e.g., accuracy, relevance to the question, logical consistency, completeness).
2. **Compare each candidate answer** step-by-step with respect to these criteria. Clearly show your reasoning process.
3. **Decide whether any of the three answers is appropriate and accurate enough to be selected.**
 - If **one** candidate is suitable, select it and explain why it is better than the other two.
 - If **none** of the candidates are suitable, provide your own short and long answers that directly address the question, and explain why the candidates were not appropriate.
4. **Output the final decision** as the final selected long answer or your own generated long answer.

When you output an answer, please follow these rules:

- Show your full reasoning process as a step-by-step explanation before providing the final decision.
- Short Answer formatting rules
 - Preserve the entity's **full official name**.
 - Type 2 → "Diabetes mellitus, type 2"
 - Factor VIII → "Factor VIII deficiency"
 - 2 → "Chromosome 2"
 - Carpenter's → "Carpenter's syndrome"
 - NPH → "Normal Pressure Hydrocephalus"
 - For yes/no questions, reply **exactly** Yes or No.
- If you generate your own answers, do so with the same thoroughness and format.
- You are strongly required to follow the specified output format; conclude your response with the phrase "Therefore the answer is [ANSWER]."

User prompt

Here is the original question:
{question}

Below are three candidate answers, each with a short and long version:

1. Candidate A:

- Short Answer: {Short answer from Web Search-augmented retrieval}
- Long Answer: {Long answer from Web Search-augmented retrieval}

2. Candidate B:

- Short Answer: {Short answer from Rationale-based retrieval}
- Long Answer: {Long answer from Rationale-based retrieval}

3. Candidate C:

- Short Answer: {Short answer from Query2doc-based retrieval}
- Long Answer: {Long answer from Query2doc-based retrieval}